

Multiscale modelling of diffusion and enzymatic reaction in porous electrodes in Direct Electron Transfer mode

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Abstract

This work is dedicated to a multi-scale modelling of coupled diffusion and reaction in a porous micro-electrode operating in the Direct Electron Transfer mode. The pore-scale physico-electrochemical unsteady model is developed considering the oxygen reduction, catalyzed by an enzyme coating the pores of the electrode, coupled to the diffusion of oxygen and mass balance of enzymes. This model is formally upscaled to obtain an original closed unsteady macroscopic model operating at the electrode scale, together with the associated closure providing the effective diffusivity tensor. A validation of this model is carried out from a comparison with the solution of the initial 3D pore-scale governing equations considering the bilirubin oxydase as the catalyst. The relevance and accuracy of the macroscale model are proved allowing a considerable simulation speedup. It is further employed to successfully predict experimental voltammetry results obtained with porous gold electrodes fonctionnalized with a bilirubin oxidase mutant (BOD S362C).

Keywords: Porous electrode, Direct Electron Transfer, Bilirubin Oxidase, Diffusion reaction, Volume averaging method

1. Introduction

Over the past two decades, porous electrodes, featuring a high specific surface area (*i.e.* a large internal solid-fluid interface per unit volume), have been efficiently developed to make miniaturized electro-devices such as bio-batteries, bio-actuators and bio-sensors [1, 2, 3, 4]. Such electrodes can provide electrical current several orders of magnitude larger than simple flat electrodes of the same size [5, 6]. A classical way to synthesize porous electrodes is to form an ordered assembly of beads, for example by employing the Langmuir-Blodgett technique [7] and use it as a template as proposed by Bartlett et al. [8]. Electrodeposition of a conducting material is then performed through the layered bead assembly, followed by beads dissolution, yielding an inverse opale structure constitutive of the electrode [9]. Due to its versatility, this technique may be employed to obtain porous microstructures with tunable porosity and controllable architecture [2].

For applications in biofuel cells [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17], redox reactions can be catalyzed by enzymes which, in order to enhance their lifetime and stability, may be immobilized by entrapping the proteins [18, 19]. This can be achieved using different techniques,

16 like entrapment in a conducting polymer matrix occupying a more or less significant frac-
17 tion of the pores, or adsorption at the pore surfaces [20, 21, 22], eventually combined with
18 nano-structuration of the surfaces [23, 24]. In the former case, a mediator is employed to
19 shuttle the electrons to and from the electrode’s internal surfaces, giving rise to a so-called
20 Mediated Electron Transfer (MET) process. In contrast, in the latter case, when enzymes
21 are adsorbed on the reactive surfaces so that their active centers are positioned within the
22 electron tunnelling distance of the current collector surfaces, the process is referred to as a Di-
23 rect Electron Transfer (DET). In that case, no mediator is involved. A typical configuration
24 for such a biofuel cell is such that the two electrodes are modified by bioelectrocatalysts.
25 For example at the cathode, the multicopper oxidases (MCOs) such as bilirubin oxidase
26 (BOD) are adsorbed on the electrode surface. They consist of a type 1 copper (T1) site
27 which directly accepts electrons from the electrode, and type 2 and type 3 copper, so-called
28 trinuclear center (TNC site), receiving electrons from T1. The oxygen is then reduced to
29 water at TNC sites [15, 25]. The process will be further detailed in section 2.1. In this
30 example, chemical energy is drawn from the oxygen-glucose couple, which naturally exists in
31 physiological fluids for instance, and is converted into electrical energy resulting from oxygen
32 reduction at the cathode and glucose oxidation at the anode.

33 Modelling of transport and reactions in porous electrodes has often been treated with
34 empirical macroscopic models even in the case without enzymes (see for instance [26, 27,
35 28, 29, 30]). As a consequence, all the features of the physico-electrochemical mechanisms
36 (coupling diffusion and reaction in the unsteady regime for example) and of the geometrical
37 structure, in particular for porous electrodes, are not elucidated. More formal approaches
38 were proposed [31, 32, 33] without however any explicit closure to relate the pore-scale
39 microstructure to the effective macroscale parameters, in particular, the effective diffusivity.
40 In a recent work, a thorough multiscale model for direct oxygen reduction reaction in a
41 porous electrode was developed by upscaling the pore-scale model and formally obtain a
42 closed macroscale description using the volume averaging method [34]. It was employed to
43 determine the optimal macroscopic thickness of a porous electrode [35, 36] and it has been
44 extended to the case of two serial reactions for oxygen reduction [37].

45 In the case of reactions catalyzed by enzymes in the DET (or MET) mode, modelling is
46 more complex, and this has motivated empirical analytic expressions of the current density
47 to fit experimental data curves [38, 39]. Moreover, in these works, steady-state conditions
48 were assumed for which surface concentrations of enzymes are supposed to be constant and
49 oxygen supply is continuous. Some other studies were carried for a simple shape non-porous
50 electrode, assuming steady-state [40] or non steady-state conditions [41]. In an interesting
51 work by Do *et al.* [42], a non-steady macroscopic model was proposed. The reported model
52 is 1D and electrode scale equations are not explicitly derived, remaining unclosed since the
53 effective diffusion coefficient is empirically correlated to the porosity of the material. The
54 model was successfully tested to predict experimental observations in steady-state conditions.
55 For practical use, a general 3D unsteady and closed macroscopic model operating at the
56 electrode scale is highly desirable, including all the available information of the physico-
57 electrochemical processes at the underlying pore-scale.

58 In this context, the present work aims at a detailed multiscale modelling of a porous
59 electrode operating in the DET mode, following an upscaling approach. The development
60 represents a complex task due to the coupling of reactions, unsteadiness and non linearity
61 of the overall problem. The purpose is first to provide the set of balance equations, initial
62 and boundary conditions governing the transient coupled process for oxygen diffusion and
63 catalyzed enzymatic reactions in the DET regime within the pores. In this configuration, the
64 pore-scale mass transfer of oxygen is essentially diffusive, while a cathodic oxygen reduction
65 reaction with enzymatic catalysis is considered partially using the framework proposed by
66 Hexter and co-workers [43, 44] for the reaction scheme. Upscaling is performed with the vol-
67 ume averaging method [45] to obtain a new and original macroscopic model at the electrode
68 scale that is further validated both numerically and with experimental data. This model is
69 fully unsteady, yielding the evolution of both the enzyme and oxygen concentrations. It is
70 formally derived from the pore-scale equations with a closure providing the effective param-
71 eters. This approach has not been reported in the literature so far although this is of prime
72 importance as was raised as a conclusion in a recent review by Rajendran *et al.* [46].

73 The remainder of the article is organized as follows. In Section 2, the pore-scale diffu-
74 sion/reaction model at the microscale is developed for the enzymatic Direct Electron Transfer
75 regime. In this context, an electrochemical model for the reduction reaction of oxygen cat-
76 alyzed by BOD is proposed. It is coupled to mass transfer by diffusion of oxygen and mass
77 balance of enzyme under non steady-state conditions. To derive a macroscopic model that
78 is much more effective in terms of computational resources, an upscaling procedure of the
79 pore-scale model is applied, the main steps of which are summarized in Section 3 for the
80 sake of conciseness. More details for this derivation are reported in Appendix A. In Section
81 4, 3D direct numerical simulations of the pore-scale model are carried out and their results
82 are compared to those obtained from simulations of the 1D macroscopic model to validate
83 the upscaling approach. Experimental details, describing the materials and methods for the
84 electrocatalytic characterization of macroporous gold electrodes are provided in Section 5.
85 The ability of the macroscopic model to predict experimental voltammetry results, obtained
86 from these electrodes modified by BOD adsorption and immersed in a buffer solution, is
87 presented in this section. Conclusions are proposed in Section 6.

88 2. Pore-scale diffusion/reaction coupled model

89 In this section, the unsteady pore-scale model for diffusion and reaction in a porous
90 electrode, whose internal surface has been modified by the adsorption of BOD enzyme, is
91 developed. The oxygen reduction reaction scheme within the layer containing the enzyme
92 at the electrode surface is assumed to take place in the DET mode. Without any restriction
93 in the physical description of the electrochemical process, the analysis is carried out at the
94 cathode.

95 The porous electrode, immersed in a reactive solution, occupies the spatial domain Ω
96 composed of the solid phase Ω_s and the fluid phase Ω_f with the interface denoted by $\Gamma_{sf} =$
97 $\Omega_f \cap \Omega_s$ nearby which the oxygen reduction reaction takes place. The electrode is supplied by
98 diffusion of oxygen from the bulk fluid, occupying the domain Ω_e , surrounding the electrode.

99 Electron exchange during the reduction of oxygen results from a double electron transfer
 100 which may be described by a pair of reactions as proposed in section 2.1.

101 *2.1. Electrochemical process*

102 The BOD enzyme is supposed to be immobilized at the surface Γ_{sf} of the cathodic
 103 electrode to catalyze the oxygen reduction. It contains type 1 copper, forming T1 sites,
 104 while TNC sites are composed of type 2 and type 3 copper [14]. In the DET mode, electrons
 105 from the electrode's internal surface are accepted by type 1 copper (T1 sites) where the
 106 enzyme reduction occurs. They are transferred from T1 to the TNC (T2 and T3) sites
 107 which remain at a tunneling distance from the pore surfaces and where reduction of oxygen
 108 takes place [38, 25] (see Fig. 1). The reaction scheme at an electrode surface modified with
 109 BOD may hence be described following the approach proposed by Hexter and co-workers
 110 [43, 44] for the reaction of hydrogenases during the reduction of H^+ to H_2 . In these works,
 111 the electrode is supposed to be continuously supplied with H^+ so that the mass transfer
 112 problem is neglected yielding a description under steady-state conditions. On the contrary,
 113 a fully unsteady description is considered here.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of electron transfer from the electrode surface to the T1 site and further to a TNC site where oxygen reduction occurs

114 In the case of oxygen reduction of interest here, the catalytic reaction in the DET mode
 115 may be written in the following form

where n_1 is the number of transferred electrons involved in the reduction of the enzyme which oxidized and reduced forms are denoted by Ox and Re respectively. In the case of

BOD, which is further considered for validation and comparison with experiments in sections 4 and 5, $n_1 = 1$ [38]. Note that the direct reaction pathway for oxygen reduction has been assumed in (1b) as this was confirmed to be the preferential one in experimental observations with the BOD enzyme [47]. The electron transfer rate constants k_{1a} and k_{1c} are given by the Butler-Volmer relationships

$$k_{1c} = k_0 \exp \left[-\frac{n_1 \alpha_1 F (E - E_{Ox/Re}^0)}{RT} \right] \quad (2a)$$

$$k_{1a} = k_0 \exp \left[\frac{n_1 (1 - \alpha_1) F (E - E_{Ox/Re}^0)}{RT} \right] \quad (2b)$$

where k_0 and α_1 are the standard rate constant and electron transfer coefficient, E and $E_{Ox/Re}^0$ the electrode potential and the potential of the redox center, F , R and T the Faraday's constant, gas constant and temperature respectively. Similarly, for the oxygen reduction, the catalytic rate constants k_{2c} and k_{2a} , representative of the internal driving energy within the enzyme, take the following expressions

$$k_{2c} = k'_2 \exp \left[\frac{-n_2 \alpha_2 F (E_{Ox/Re}^0 - E_{O_2/H_2O})}{RT} \right] \quad (3a)$$

$$k_{2a} = k_2 \exp \left[\frac{n_2 (1 - \alpha_2) F (E_{Ox/Re}^0 - E_{O_2/H_2O})}{RT} \right] \quad (3b)$$

116 where E_{O_2/H_2O} is the thermodynamic equilibrium potential of the couple O_2/H_2O , α_2 the
 117 electron transfer coefficient associated with this reaction and n_2 the number of electrons
 118 involved. It should be noted that the oxygen reduction in reaction (1b) can be considered
 119 as irreversible. For both the validation of the macroscopic model and the comparison with
 120 experiments presented in the following sections, the backward reaction in (1b) is ignored and
 121 k_{2a} was hence taken equal to zero for consistency, even if this parameter is formally kept for
 122 completeness in the theoretical development reported below, which may straightforwardly
 123 be used for an other type of system.

Although four electrons are required for the reduction of O_2 in (1b), a different value might be relevant for n_2 depending on the limiting step governing the electron transfer for this reaction. A further detailed discussion of this feature is beyond the scope of the present work and, as will be seen later, the use of the models derived in the following sections does not explicitly require the value of n_2 to be specified. In addition, it is worth noticing that the unit of the rate constants k_{1c} , k_{1a} and k_{2a} is $1/s$ whereas that of k_{2c} is $m^3/mol/s$. The latter is in contrast with that of the corresponding constant used in the work by Hexter *et al.* [43] which was restricted to steady conditions that are not retained here as this might be insufficient in practical situations. From the oxygen reduction reaction at TNC sites (see (1b)), the associated reaction rate, R_{O_2} , can be expressed according to the following Butler-Volmer relationship [48]

$$R_{O_2} = -k_{2c} c_{Re} c_{O_2} + k_{2a} c_{Ox} \quad (4)$$

124 In the following, a fully coupled diffusion-reaction model is developed, in which concentra-
 125 tions of all species (enzyme and oxygen) are time-dependent to describe the entire unsteady
 126 process.

127 2.2. Physical model at the pore-scale

128 Modelling starts with the initial and boundary value problem governing diffusion of oxy-
 129 gen, which is assumed to be a Fickian process, coupled to oxido-reduction mechanisms inside
 130 the pores. Since the enzyme is immobilized at the pore surfaces, no diffusion is taken into
 131 account for this species. The pore-scale model can hence be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{I.C.1} \quad \frac{\partial c_{Re}}{\partial t} &= k_{1c}c_{Ox} - k_{1a}c_{Re} - k_{2c}c_{Re}c_{O_2} + k_{2a}c_{Ox} && \text{at } \Gamma_{sf} && (5a) \\
 & c_{Ox} + c_{Re} = c_E^t && \text{at } \Gamma_{sf} && (5b) \\
 & c_{Re} = \mathcal{F}_{Re}(\mathbf{r}) && \mathbf{r} \in \Gamma_{sf}, t = 0 && (5c) \\
 \text{B.C.1} \quad \frac{\partial c_{O_2}}{\partial t} &= \nabla \cdot (\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla c_{O_2}) && \text{in } \Omega_f && (5d) \\
 & -\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla c_{O_2} = -R_{O_2} && \text{at } \Gamma_{sf} && (5e) \\
 \text{I.C.2} \quad & c_{O_2} = \mathcal{F}_{O_2}(\mathbf{r}) && \mathbf{r} \in \Omega_f, t = 0 && (5f) \\
 \text{B.C.2} \quad & c_{O_2} = \mathcal{G}_{O_2}(\mathbf{r}, t) && \mathbf{r} \in A_{fe}, \forall t && (5g)
 \end{aligned}$$

where c_{Re} , c_{Ox} and c_{O_2} are the surface concentrations of *Re* and *Ox* and the bulk oxygen concentration respectively. The total enzyme concentration c_E^t (see Eq. (5b)) is considered to remain constant at any time whereas mass conservation of *Re* in Eq. (5a) results from reactions (1). In the oxygen mass conservation equation (5d) and in the boundary condition in Eq. (5e), \mathcal{D}_{O_2} is the molecular diffusion coefficient of O_2 in the fluid saturating the pores while \mathbf{n} is the unit normal vector to Γ_{sf} pointing out of Ω_f . The reaction rate, R_{O_2} , is given by Eq. (4). In the expression of the external boundary condition B.C.2, $A_{fe} = \Omega_f \cap \Omega_e$ is the entrance and/or exit boundaries of the fluid phase, Ω_f , from/into the external bulk fluid, Ω_e , in which the electrode is immersed. The solution of Eqs. (5) yields the oxygen and enzymes concentration fields from which the current density, j , can be obtained from the reaction rate at T1 sites (1a). It is given by

$$j = n_1 F (k_{1a}c_{Re} - k_{1c}c_{Ox}) \quad (6)$$

that can be further used to compute the total current, I , available at the electrode according to

$$I = \int_{\Gamma_{sf}} j dS \quad (7)$$

132 Although the solution of Eqs. (5) can be sought using a Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS)
 133 as will be reported for validation purposes in section 4.1, a macroscopic model is necessary
 134 for the characterization and prediction of the behavior of an electrode. Moreover, as in-
 135 dicated in a previous work dedicated to modelling of electrodes in the absence of enzyme
 136 [34], computational resources required by DNS are substantial and a macroscopic model is

137 much more efficient for practical use. With these objectives in mind, the pore-scale model is
 138 upscaled, carrying coupling and non linearities, in order to obtain a macroscopic description
 139 that is provided in the next section.

140 3. Macroscopic model

141 The macroscopic model, operating at the electrode scale, is derived from the initial and
 142 boundary value pore-scale problem using the volume averaging method [45]. For the sake
 143 of brevity, only the main result of this procedure is reported below while the details of the
 144 formal derivation are provided in Appendix A.

Let V , of measure V and size r_0 , be the averaging volume including the solid and fluid domains V_s and V_f (of volumes V_s and V_f , respectively) sharing the solid/fluid interface A_{sf} of measure A_{sf} . The porosity, ε_f , and specific area, a_v , of the porous material are respectively defined by

$$\varepsilon_f = V_f/V \quad (8a)$$

$$a_v = A_{sf}/V \quad (8b)$$

Figure 2: Averaging volume for a two-phase system.

The upscaling process makes use of the superficial, intrinsic and area averages of the concentration fields for oxygen and reduced enzyme that are respectively defined by

$$\langle c_{O_2} \rangle |_{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_f(\mathbf{x})} c_{O_2} |_{\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{y}} dV \quad (9a)$$

$$\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{1}{V_f} \int_{V_f(\mathbf{x})} c_{O_2} |_{\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{y}} dV \quad (9b)$$

$$\langle c_X \rangle_{sf} |_{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{1}{A_{sf}} \int_{A_{sf}(\mathbf{x})} c_X |_{\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{y}} dA, \quad X = O_2, Re \quad (9c)$$

with the straightforward relationship $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle = \varepsilon_f \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ and where \mathbf{x} locates the centroid of the averaging volume while $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{x}$ locates any point within \mathbf{V}_f relative to \mathbf{x} (see Fig. 2). For the sake of simplicity, the subscript referring to the location may be dropped, unless necessary. The derivation of the upscaled model is subject to a scale hierarchy defined by $\ell_p \ll r_0 \ll L$, ℓ_p being the characteristic pore size and L the macroscopic size of the electrode. The upscaling procedure is carried out according to the four main steps reported in Appendix A and under the constraints on the kinetic number, Ki , and time scale respectively given by

$$Ki = \frac{k_{2c}\ell_p c_E^t}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \ll 1 \quad (10a)$$

$$t \gg \mathcal{O} \left[\frac{\ell_p^2}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}, \frac{1}{k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a} + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f} \right] \quad (10b)$$

Under these circumstances, the macroscopic model, including the enzyme and oxygen effective mass conservation equations operating at the electrode scale, can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}}{\partial t} = - (k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a}) \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2c} \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + (k_{1c} + k_{2a}) c_E^t \quad (11a)$$

$$\langle c_{Ox} \rangle_{sf} = c_E^t - \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \quad (11b)$$

$$\varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\varepsilon_f \mathbf{D}_{eff} \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f) - k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v (\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - c_E^t) \quad (11c)$$

In the macroscopic diffusion-reaction equation (11c), \mathbf{D}_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient given by

$$\mathbf{D}_{eff} = \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\mathbf{I} + \frac{1}{V_f} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} b dA \right) \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{b} is the solution of the following closure problem (see also Eqs. (A.33) in Appendix A)

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{b} = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathbf{V}_f \quad (13a)$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{b} = -\mathbf{n} \quad \text{at } \mathbf{A}_{sf} \quad (13b)$$

$$\langle \mathbf{b} \rangle^f = 0 \quad (13c)$$

$$\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r} + \ell_i \mathbf{e}_i) \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (13d)$$

145 This problem is intrinsic to the porous structure, which means that its solution only depends
146 on the microgeometry of the pore space. To obtain this result, it must be noted that
147 the averaging domain, \mathbf{V} , was taken as a Representative Elementary Volume of the porous
148 structure that was further considered as pseudo periodic so that the closure problem is solved
149 on a unit cell whose periodic lattice vectors are $\ell_i \mathbf{e}_i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$).

150 Equations (11), together with the initial and boundary conditions on $\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}$ and $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$,
 151 form the new macroscopic effective model of coupled diffusion-reaction for a porous electrode
 152 operating in the DET mode.

The expression of the current from the macroscopic surface average of the reduced enzyme concentration can now be derived. The surface average of Eq. (6) yields

$$\langle j \rangle_{sf} = n_1 F \left(k_{1a} \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{1c} \left(c_E^t - \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \right) \right) \quad (14)$$

from which the current per unit volume of the unit cell representative of the medium, i_v , can be deduced as $i_v = \langle j \rangle_{sf} A_{sf}/V = a_v \langle j \rangle_{sf}$. The total current, I , delivered by the electrode is hence given by $I = \int_{\Omega} i_v dV$, *i.e.*

$$I = a_v \int_{\Omega} \langle j \rangle_{sf} dV \quad (15)$$

153 4. Numerical results and discussions

154 The relevance of the prediction obtained with the new original macroscopic model is
 155 assessed by a comparison with DNS of the pore-scale problem. This is carried out on a model
 156 porous structure whose unit cell, of size ℓ_R , is a face-centered cubic (FCC) arrangement of
 157 spherical pores, of diameter $d_s \equiv \ell_p$, interconnected to each other through circular windows
 158 of diameter d_c (see Fig. 3).

159 4.1. Direct numerical simulation of the pore-scale model

160 The 3D numerical voltammetry experiments were performed on a computational domain
 161 represented in Fig. 3. The porous electrode is composed of periodic FCC unit cells in
 162 the z -direction, between $z = -L_e$, where the electrically conducting electrode support is
 163 positioned, and $z = 0$, where the electrode is in contact with the bulk fluid saturating the
 164 pores. The fluid region, Ω_e , between $z = 0$ and $z = L_N$, corresponds to the diffusion layer
 165 where oxygen molecular diffusion takes place. Periodic boundary conditions are applied in
 166 the x and y directions. This is justified by the fact that the electrode length is supposed to
 167 be much larger than ℓ_R and that the same holds for its lateral extension, if the electrode is
 168 a plane one. If it is circular, L_e is supposed to be much smaller than its mean radius. A
 169 zero flux condition is imposed at $z = -L_e$ while a constant oxygen concentration, $c_{O_2} = c_{O_2}^0$,
 170 is considered at the interface of the diffusion layer with the rest of the bulk fluid, $z = L_N$.
 171 The initial concentration of oxygen is supposed to be uniform equal to $c_{O_2}^0$. In addition, only
 172 oxidized enzyme is assumed to be present at the initial state, leading to $c_{Re} = 0$ at $t = 0$.

Figure 3: 3D domain for the direct numerical simulation.

The pore-scale problem in Eqs. (5), coupled to the diffusion of O_2 in the diffusion layer, can be rewritten in a dimensionless form using ℓ_R , $\frac{\ell_R^2}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}$, $c_{O_2}^0$ and c_E^t as the reference length, time, oxygen and enzyme surface concentrations. Denoting dimensionless quantities with the superscript $*$, this coupled non-linear problem is given by

$$\frac{\partial c_{O_2}^*}{\partial t^*} = \nabla^{*2} c_{O_2}^* \quad \text{in } \Omega_f \cup \Omega_e \quad (16a)$$

$$\text{B.C.1} \quad -\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla^* c_{O_2}^* = 0 \quad \text{at } z^* = -L_e^* \quad (16b)$$

$$\text{B.C.2} \quad c_{O_2}^* = 1 \quad \text{at } z^* = L_N^* \quad (16c)$$

$$\text{B.C.3} \quad -\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla^* c_{O_2}^* = \frac{\ell_R c_E^t}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \left(k_{2c} c_{Re}^* c_{O_2}^* - \frac{k_{2a}}{c_{O_2}^0} (1 - c_{Re}^*) \right) \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{sf} \quad (16d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial c_{Re}^*}{\partial t^*} = \frac{\ell_R^2}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} & \left(- \left(k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a} + k_{2c} c_{O_2}^0 c_{O_2}^* \right) c_{Re}^* \right. \\ & \left. + k_{1c} + k_{2a} \right) \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{sf} \quad (16e) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{I.C.1} \quad c_{O_2}^* = 1 \quad \text{in } \Omega_f \cup \Omega_e \text{ at } t^* = 0 \quad (16f)$$

$$\text{I.C.2} \quad c_{Re}^* = 0 \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{sf} \text{ at } t^* = 0 \quad (16g)$$

$$c_{O_2}^*(x^*, y^*, z^*) = c_{O_2}^*(x^* + 1, y^* + 1, z^*), \quad \text{in } \Omega_f \quad (16h)$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla^* c_{O_2}^*(x^*, y^*, z^*) = \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla^* c_{O_2}^*(x^* + 1, y^* + 1, z^*), \quad \text{in } \Omega_f \quad (16i)$$

$$c_{Re}^*(x^*, y^*, z^*) = c_{Re}^*(x^* + 1, y^* + 1, z^*), \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{sf} \quad (16j)$$

173

174 Voltammetry simulation, with a scan-rate $r_E = 5 \text{ mV/s}$ and an initial potential value of
 175 0.6 V , was carried out with $L_e^* = 10$ and $L_N = 20 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ (*i.e.* $L_N^* \simeq 12$). Values of the other

176 physical parameters are reported in Table. 1. It should be noted that k_{2a} is taken equal to
 177 zero since the reduction of O_2 is considered as irreversible. Since BOD is the enzyme for the
 178 catalytic reaction, $n_1 = 1$ [38].

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Ideal gas constant	R	8.314	$Jmol^{-1}K^{-1}$
Faraday's constant	F	96485.33	$Cmol^{-1}$
Number of transferred electron	n_1	1	—
Electron transfer coefficient	α_1	0.5	—
Standard potential vs. $E_{Ag/AgCl}^0$	$E_{Ox/Re}^0$	0.41	V
Equilibrium potential vs. $E_{Ag/AgCl}^0$	E_{O_2/H_2O}	0.619	V
Scan rate	r_E	5	mVs^{-1}
Temperature	T	298	K
Bulk concentration	$c_{O_2}^0$	1.2	$mol\ m^{-3}$
Total surface concentration of enzymes	c_E^t	10^{-8}	$mol\ m^{-2}$
Diffusion coefficient	\mathcal{D}_{O_2}	$2 \cdot 10^{-9}$	m^2s^{-1}
Standard rate constant	k_0	10	s^{-1}
Electron transfer rate constant	k_{2c}	485.83	$m^3mol^{-1}s^{-1}$
Spherical pore diameter	d_s	1.17	μm
Relative pore connection window size	d_c/d_s	15%	—
Size of the periodic unit cell	ℓ_R	1.678	μm

Table 1: Parameters used for the simulations

179 The software COMSOL Multiphysics (ver. 5.4), with physics-controlled mesh including
 180 extremely fine grid blocks composed of 10^7 tetrahedral elements in the overall domain, was
 181 used to solve this problem. The typical computational time is about 12 hours on a Dell
 182 PowerEdge 430 - 2 processors Intel Xeon E5-2630v3.

183 Dimensionless oxygen concentration fields obtained from DNS in Ω_f and Ω_e are repre-
 184 sented in Fig. 4 at $t = 10\ s, 55\ s$ and $70\ s$, highlighting the coupled diffusion-reaction process
 185 inside the porous electrode and showing the oxygen concentration decrease with time. In
 186 this configuration, $Ki = 10^{-3}$, a value that satisfies the constraint in (10a).

Figure 4: Normalized O_2 concentration fields, $c_{O_2}^*$, at $t = 10$ s, 55 s and 70 s, the corresponding potential values being $E = 0.55$ V, 0.325 V and $E = 0.25$ V, respectively.

187 These results can now be directly compared to simulations of the macroscopic model and
 188 this is the object of the following section.

189 4.2. Solution of the macroscopic model and comparisons with DNS

190 Our aim now is to explore the relevance of the macroscopic model, its performance to
 191 predict the average concentrations and the current delivered by the electrode. Since the FCC
 192 structure under consideration here is isotropic, $\mathbf{D}_{eff} = \mathcal{D}_{eff} \mathbf{I}$ (\mathbf{I} being the identity tensor) and
 193 the macroscopic model reduces to 1D. The macroscopic computational domain constituted
 194 by the 1D effective medium for the electrode and the diffusion layer is represented in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: 1D configuration for the macroscopic numerical simulation.

195

Using the same reference quantities, the dimensionless macroscopic problem can be writ-

ten as

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f}{\partial t^*} &= \varepsilon_f \mathbf{D}_{eff}^* \frac{\partial^2 \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f}{\partial z^{*2}} \\ &\quad - \frac{a_v \ell_R^2 c_E^t}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2} c_{O_2}^0} \left(k_{2c} c_{O_2}^0 \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f \langle c_{Re}^* \rangle_{sf} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + k_{2a} \left(\langle c_{Re}^* \rangle_{sf} - 1 \right) \right) \end{aligned} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (17a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle c_{Re}^* \rangle_{sf}}{\partial t^*} &= \frac{\ell_R^2}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \left(-(k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a}) \langle c_{Re}^* \rangle_{sf} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - k_{2c} c_{O_2}^0 \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f \langle c_{Re}^* \rangle_{sf} + k_{1c} + k_{2a} \right) \end{aligned} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (17b)$$

$$\text{B.C.1} \quad \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f = c_{O_2}^* \quad \text{at } z^* = 0 \quad (17c)$$

$$\text{B.C.2} \quad \varepsilon_f \mathbf{D}_{eff}^* \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f}{\partial z^*} = \frac{\partial c_{O_2}^*}{\partial z^*} \quad \text{at } z^* = 0 \quad (17d)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_{O_2}^*}{\partial t^*} = \frac{\partial^2 c_{O_2}^*}{\partial z^{*2}} \quad \text{in } \Omega_e \quad (17e)$$

$$\text{B.C.3} \quad \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f}{\partial z^*} = 0 \quad \text{at } z^* = -L_e^* \quad (17f)$$

$$\text{B.C.4} \quad c_{O_2}^* = 1 \quad \text{at } z^* = L_N^* \quad (17g)$$

$$\text{I.C. 1} \quad \langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f = 1 \quad \text{in } \Omega \text{ at } t^* = 0 \quad (17h)$$

$$\text{I.C. 2} \quad \langle c_{Re}^* \rangle_{sf} = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \text{ at } t^* = 0 \quad (17i)$$

$$\text{I.C. 3} \quad c_{O_2}^* = 1 \quad \text{in } \Omega_e \text{ at } t^* = 0 \quad (17j)$$

196 In Eq. (17a), \mathbf{D}_{eff}^* represents the dimensionless effective diffusion coefficient, $\mathbf{D}_{eff}^* =$
 197 $\mathbf{D}_{eff}/\mathcal{D}_{O_2}$. Prior to the solution of the above model, the closure problem in Eqs. (13)
 198 was solved over a periodic FCC unit cell. Both the closure and macroscopic problems were
 199 solved with COMSOL Multiphysics (ver. 5.4).

200 Voltammetry simulation using the 1D-macroscopic effective model in Eqs (17) was car-
 201 ried out in the same conditions as for the 3D DNS at the microscale presented in Section
 202 4.1, *i.e.* using the parameters indicated in Table 1 with $L_e^* = 10$ and $L_N^* \simeq 12$. For this mi-
 203 crostructure, $\varepsilon_f = 0.763$, $a_v^* = 5.985$ and $\varepsilon_f \mathbf{D}_{eff}^* = 0.364$. The mesh used for this simulation
 204 is made of ~ 800 elements. The pore-scale fields of $c_{O_2}^*$ and c_{Re}^* were averaged in each unit
 205 cell over \mathbf{V}_f and \mathbf{A}_{sf} respectively and then compared to $\langle c_{O_2}^* \rangle^f$ and $\langle c_{Re}^* \rangle_{sf}$ obtained from
 206 the solution of the macroscopic model.

207 The dimensionless oxygen concentration profiles inside the porous electrode, obtained
 208 from the 3D-DNS and 1D simulation, are represented at the three times $t = 10$ s, 55 s and
 209 70 s in Fig. 6. This concentration decreases with time as a result of the reduction reaction
 210 while its gradient increases at the electrode-diffusion layer interface ($z^* = 0$) and hence

211 inside the electrode. As shown on this figure, the agreement between the two approaches is
 212 excellent.

Figure 6: Comparison of the concentration profiles of oxygen obtained from the 3D DNS (micromodel) and 1D (macromodel) simulation. All the data employed to carry out both the pore-scale DNS and the macroscale simulation are mentioned in the text above and in Table 1.

213 Similarly, the dimensionless reduced enzyme surface concentration profiles obtained with
 214 both the micro and macro-scale models are reported in Fig. 7. Again, the comparison
 215 between the two shows an excellent agreement, confirming the validity of the new macroscopic
 216 model derived in this work.

Figure 7: Comparison of reduced enzyme concentration profiles obtained from the 3D DNS (micromodel) and 1D (macromodel) simulation.

217 As a final important check, the interest must now be focused on the current curves
 218 in voltamograms. The current was computed by making use of Eqs. (6) and (7) in the
 219 microscale approach and with Eqs. (14) and (15) involving the average reduced enzyme
 220 concentration obtained from the solution of the macroscopic model. In Fig. 8, the current

221 per unit cross-sectional area of the electrode is represented versus the scanning potential
 222 ranging from 0.6 V to 0.1 V. A special attention must be dedicated to the mesh refinement
 223 for the 3D DNS in COMSOL Multiphysics. A tetrahedral mesh made of $\sim 3.3 \times 10^5$ elements
 224 for the domain under consideration in Fig. 3 was used to obtain converged results. As can
 225 be seen in Fig. 8, the agreement between the two approaches is again excellent.

Figure 8: Comparison between the current per unit electrode cross-sectional area versus the scanning potential during voltammetry obtained from the 3D DNS and 1D macroscopic model.

226 This again confirms the perfect agreement between the two approaches and completes
 227 the validation of the new macroscopic model which provides a powerful tool to predict the
 228 macroscopic behavior of a porous electrode operating in the DET mode. In addition it must
 229 be emphasized that this original macroscopic approach allows a considerable computational
 230 speedup. Indeed, in the case under consideration in this section, the macroscale solution
 231 requires only 4 seconds, which, compared to the corresponding 3D DNS with the above
 232 mentioned mesh (85 minutes), represents a speedup of about 1300.

233 In the following section, the ability of the macroscopic model to predict the current-to-
 234 potential relationship characteristics of an electrode is reported through comparisons with
 235 experimental voltammetry results obtained with a porous gold electrode coated with BOD
 236 as the bioelectrocatalyst at the cathode.

237 5. Comparison with experimental data

238 In this section, the capability of the macroscopic model to predict voltammetry experi-
 239 mental data is investigated. To this purpose, experiments were carried out on porous gold
 240 electrodes.

241 5.1. Experimental details

242 The three main steps of the experimental protocol consist in the electrode synthesis, the
 243 enzyme immobilization and the electrocatalytic characterization.

244 Electrode Synthesis

245 Cylindrical macroporous gold electrodes were prepared using a Langmuir-Blodgett tech-
246 nique as shortly described in the introduction and detailed in [8, 9, 2]. In brief, silica beads
247 with a diameter of 1170 nm ($d_s = 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ is taken as an accurate enough value) were
248 spread from an ethanol/chloroform (20% v/v-80% v/v) suspension at the water-air inter-
249 face of a Langmuir-Blodgett trough. An optimal monolayer of silica beads was obtained at
250 the water-air interface after compression by closing the moveable barriers. Then, multiple
251 silica particle layers were transferred onto gold wires of 250 μm in diameter and 4 cm in
252 length. This was achieved by repeating the dipping and withdrawing process at a speed of
253 1.2 mm/min. After the formation of the silica template layers on the surface, Elevate[®] Gold
254 7990 was used for the gold electrodeposition over a length of 2 cm by applying a constant
255 potential of -0.6 V. The number of macroporous layers is controlled by following the current
256 oscillations. After dissolving the silica particles in 5% hydrofluoric acid for several minutes,
257 the final macroporous gold electrode is obtained as an inverse opale gold structure. Four
258 electrodes were prepared, having 3, 7, 11 and 19 half-layers (HL) of pores. At this stage, the
259 internal pore surfaces were coated with a genetically engineered variant of Bilirubin oxidase
260 from *M. oryzae* whose serine in position 362 was replaced by a cysteine (BOD S362C) [49].
261 This was performed over the porous zone being 2 cm long, corresponding to a surface area of
262 the initial wire of 15 mm². The actual active surface area depends on the thickness of the
263 porous layers of the electrode. There is a linear correspondence between the active area of
264 the porous electrode and the number of porous half layers, as reported recently [50].

265 Enzyme Immobilization

266 A 0.1 mM BOD S362C ($516 \pm 38 \text{ U/mg}$) solution was prepared in 50 mM phosphate
267 buffer (pH 6.0). Since the cysteine residue on the outer surface of bilirubin oxidase is close
268 to the T1 active center, the interaction between the thiol group on the cysteine residue and
269 the gold surface allows the formation of a self-assembled monolayer of BOD S362Cs on the
270 internal surface of the pores. This allows a proper orientation of the BOD on the electrode
271 surface and favors the interfacial electron transfer. The macroporous gold electrode was
272 dipped into the enzyme solution after being treated with plasma for 15 min. Vacuum was
273 then applied for 3 min to ensure an efficient penetration of enzymes into the whole porous
274 structure. The electrode was kept at 4 °C overnight. After rinsing with distilled water and
275 with 0.1 M PBS pH 7.2 under stirring, the electroenzymatic O_2 reduction was performed
276 with the BOD modified electrodes.

277 Electrocatalytic characterization

278 All electrochemical measurements were performed with an Autolab PGSTAT101 poten-
279 tiostat monitored by a PC running Nova 1.6. A Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) was used as a reference
280 electrode, and a cylindrical carbon sheet was employed as an auxiliary electrode. For the
281 electrochemical reduction, the buffer solution was purged with O_2 for 15 min. Then, the
282 electrodes were dipped into the buffer solution maintained at ambient temperature while a
283 slow flow of O_2 was kept above it inside a sealed cell for the O_2 concentration to remain
284 constant in the buffer. Voltammetry experiments were carried out in the potential range
285 from 0.6 V to 0.15 V with a scan rate of 5 mV/s. The temperature was 25 °C for these

286 experiments. Each experiments was at least performed in triplicate.

287 5.2. Voltammetry interpretation

288 The templating procedure leads to a rather compact bead arrangement so that an FCC
 289 periodic cell represents a reasonable model for the resulting structure. This was observed
 290 in the work reported in [9] and further confirmed in a recent in-depth analysis of the 3D
 291 microstructure extracted from FIB-SEM imaging [51]. The relative size of the pore connec-
 292 tion window, d_c/d_s was taken equal to 15%, which can be considered as the minimum value
 293 for this manufacturing process [52]. With these structural parameters, the effective diffusion
 294 coefficient was computed to be $\varepsilon_f D_{eff}^* = 0.364$.

295 Interpretation of the experimental voltammetry data is carried out using a fitting pro-
 296 cedure on some of the parameters involved in the macroscale model in Eqs. (17) that are
 297 unknown a priori. To do so, k_0 , k_{2c} , α_1 and $E_{Ox/re}^0$ were estimated using a fitting procedure
 298 in the least square sense on data obtained with the 11HL electrode. It must be reminded
 299 that the individual values of n_2 and α_2 are not required and that k_{2a} is taken equal to zero
 300 in agreement with the irreversibility of oxygen reduction¹. The fitted resulting values are
 301 reported in Table 2 and were kept the same to predict the voltammetry results on the other
 302 electrodes.

k_0 (s^{-1})	k_{2c} ($m^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$)	$\alpha_1(-)$	$E_{Ox/Re}^0(V)$
10.5	25.9	0.46	0.405

Table 2: Parameters fitted on the voltammetry results obtained with the 11HL electrode and used for all the other predictions employing the macroscopic model.

303 Moreover, the total concentration of enzyme, c_E^t , and the diffusion layer thickness, L_N ,
 304 that are subject to vary from one electrode to another, were fitted for each corresponding
 305 experimental data set. In fact, the diffusion layer thickness depends on the rate of oxygen
 306 depletion within the fluid in contact with the outer interface of the electrode, and this
 307 rate depends itself on the electrode thickness. Here, a simplified approach is adopted by
 308 considering L_N as constant which means that this parameter should be understood as a mean
 309 value over the period of potential scanning for each experiment. The values are indicated in
 310 Table 3; those for the remaining parameters are given in Table 1. It should be noted that
 311 the total enzyme surface concentration slightly decreases with the electrode thickness and
 312 this can be explained by the fact that, the thicker the porous material, the more difficult is
 313 the penetration of enzyme during the coating process deeper in the pores far from the free
 314 surface of the electrode. This observation was also part of the conclusions in the work by
 315 Do *et al.* [42] on a somewhat different system.

¹The value of k_{2a} was also identified in the fitting procedure and showed to be so small that it is insensitive in the current response.

Electrodes	3HL	7HL	11HL	19HL
c_E^t ($mol\ m^{-2}$)	8.9×10^{-8}	8.07×10^{-8}	5.7×10^{-8}	4.06×10^{-8}
L_N (μm)	186	158	59	44

Table 3: Parameters used in the simulations for the fits.

316 To assess the validity of the identification procedure, a sensitivity analysis of the current
317 to all the fitted parameters was performed. The reduced sensitivity to a parameter, u , is
318 defined as $u\partial I/\partial u$, u being either k_0 , k_{2c} , α_1 , $E_{Ox/Re}^0$, L_N or c_E^t here. It was computed using
319 the 1D macroscopic model at the nominal values of each parameter identified on the 11HL
320 electrode. Sensitivities to all the parameters are represented versus the scanning potential
321 in the interval of interest in Fig. 9. This figure clearly shows that all the sensitivities
322 are significantly larger than the precision of the potentiostat used to measure the current
323 which can be estimated to be less than $0.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$ A over a very wide potential interval. In
324 addition, the sensitivities are not proportional to each other, ensuring that parameters are
325 uncorrelated. This analysis indicates that the identification procedure is robust and reliable.

Figure 9: Reduced sensitivities of the current to the parameters k_0 , k_{2c} , α_1 , $E_{Ox/Re}^0$, L_N and c_E^t at their identified values on the 11HL electrode versus the scanning potential.

326 The current versus the scanning potential obtained from our numerical simulation is
327 represented in Fig. 10 together with the experimental results. As can be seen from this
328 figure, excellent agreement is obtained for all the electrodes tested in this work over the
329 whole scanned potential interval. In this potential interval, oxygen reduction on unmodified
330 gold electrodes is not observed, because this reaction starts to occur only for potentials more
331 negative than 0.1 V vs $Ag/AgCl$. Therefore, the signals should not be disturbed by such an
332 eventual interference. The absolute value of the relative error between the two, taking the

333 experimental data as the reference, is less than 5% as shown in Fig. 11 and is distributed
 334 around 0. It remains even smaller than 3.5% when the potential is less than ~ 0.37 V for all
 335 the electrodes. Moreover, the relative error when repeating several times the experiments is
 336 very small. For example, preparing three 7HL electrodes leads to electrocatalytic currents
 337 with a standard deviation of $0.08 \cdot 10^{-5}$ A.

Figure 10: Current versus the scanning potential obtained from voltammetry numerical simulations using the macroscopic model. Comparison with the experimental data.

Figure 11: Absolute value of the relative error on the current estimated from the macroscopic model and obtained from experimental voltammetry data, taking the latter as the reference.

338 This successful comparison represents a strong validation step of the new macroscopic
 339 model derived in this work, assessing its relevance and performance to reproduce the physico-
 340 electrochemical behavior of the porous electrodes operating in the DET mode.

341 6. Conclusions

342 In this work, a new multiscale modelling for diffusion and electrochemical enzymatic
 343 reaction involved in a porous electrode operating in the DET mode was developed. The un-
 344 steady pore-scale model was provided for oxygen reduction taking into account the electron
 345 transfer process at play. An upscaling procedure, in which coupling and non-linearities were
 346 handled, was applied to obtain a closed unsteady macroscopic model valid at the electrode
 347 scale. The associate closure problem yielding the effective diffusivity tensor was provided.
 348 This approach represents an original macroscopic model that has not been reported so far in
 349 the literature. In particular, unsteadiness, which has been disregarded in existing models for
 350 enzymatic porous electrodes, was explicitly taken into account. Moreover coupling between
 351 mass transport and enzymatic reaction in a non-linear way has been carried out through
 352 the upscaling procedure. This yields new terms induced by the enzymatic reaction in the
 353 macroscopic mass conservation equations (for enzyme and oxygen). Both the micro- and
 354 macroscale models were further used in the case of oxygen reduction in the presence of BOD
 355 as a catalyst. The successful comparison of numerical voltammetry simulations, carried out
 356 on a porous model structure with the 3D pore-scale model and the macroscale model which
 357 reduces to 1D, assessed the validity of the latter. This macroscopic model was further em-
 358 ployed to predict experimental voltammetry results obtained with porous gold electrodes
 359 coated with BOD. The excellent prediction confirms the relevance of the approach and the

360 validity of this macroscopic model which provides an efficient tool operational at the electrode
 361 scale, allowing a considerable computational speedup. It also provides a mean to estimate
 362 parameters that are involved in the experiment (as for example the total enzyme concen-
 363 tration and standard rate constants). More importantly, this model represents an essential
 364 tool for the rational optimization and development of enzymatic porous electrodes. The
 365 multiscale approach developed here could be widely used for other electrochemical processes
 366 in porous media.

367 Acknowledgement

368 This work was supported by the LabEx AMADEus (ANR-10-LABX-42) within IdEx
 369 Bordeaux (ANR-10-IDEX-03-02), *i.e.* the “Investissements d’Avenir Programme” of the
 370 French government managed by the Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR). It also bene-
 371 fitted from the support of the ANR projects MOMA (ANR-17-CE08-0005) and BIO3 (ANR-
 372 16-CE19-0001). This project has also received partial funding from the European Union’s
 373 Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant
 374 agreement No 813006.

375 Appendix A Volume averaging and derivation of the upscaled model

376 In this Appendix, the upscaling procedure to derive the macroscopic diffusion/reaction
 377 equation by volume averaging the microscopic initial boundary value problem (IBVP) in
 378 Eqs. (5) is detailed. Volume averaging is applied according to the following four main steps
 379 (see Chap. 1 in [45] and [53]) and c_{O_2} is used to denote $c_{O_2}(\mathbf{r}, t)$.

380 **Step 1:** *Application of the superficial averaging operator*

381 The superficial and area averages are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle f \rangle |_{\mathbf{x}} &= \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_f(\mathbf{x})} f|_{\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{y}} dV \\ \langle f \rangle_{sf} |_{\mathbf{x}} &= \frac{1}{A_{sf}} \int_{A_{sf}(\mathbf{x})} f|_{\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{y}} dA \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

382 The superficial average operator is applied to the microscale IBVP and, with the purpose of
 383 deriving a model involving averages only, time and spatial derivation must be interchanged
 384 with volume averaging. This is achieved by using the general transport theorem, which,
 385 since the averaging volume is fixed in time and the porous medium is rigid, reduces in the
 386 present case to

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right\rangle = \frac{\partial \langle f \rangle}{\partial t} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

387 and the spatial averaging theorem (or Leibnitz rule) given by [54, 45]

$$\langle \nabla f \rangle = \nabla \langle f \rangle + \frac{1}{V} \int_{A_{sf}} \mathbf{n} f dA \quad (\text{A.3})$$

388 together with a straightforward similar form for the divergence operator.

389 With this at hand, the superficial average can be applied to the mass balance equation
 390 (5d) for O_2 and, employing the boundary condition at \mathbf{A}_{sf} , one arrives at the following
 391 average form

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot \left[\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\varepsilon_f \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \nabla \varepsilon_f + \frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} c_{O_2} dA \right) \right] \\ & - k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

392 where the intrinsic average concentration was used instead of the superficial average.

393 **Step 2: Decomposition of c_{O_2} and simplifications due to length-scale constraints**

The averaged equation (A.4) contains both average and point-wise concentrations. To remove the latter, the spatial decomposition

$$c_{O_2} = \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + \tilde{c}_{O_2} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

is introduced [55], where \tilde{c}_{O_2} is the deviation of concentration which fluctuates at a typical length-scale ℓ_p while $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ experiences significant variations at the scale L . It should be noted that a consequence of this decomposition is $\langle \tilde{c}_{O_2} \rangle^f = 0$, taking into account the scale hierarchy $\ell_p \ll L$. When this decomposition is inserted into Eq. (A.4), one gets

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot \left[\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\varepsilon_f \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \nabla \varepsilon_f + \frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f dA \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \tilde{c}_{O_2} dA \right) \right] - k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Attention must now be paid to the area integral term $\frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f dA$ on the right hand side of Eq. (A.6). This term must be evaluated at the centroid \mathbf{x} of the averaging volume \mathbf{V} and requires first the evaluation of $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ at any point $\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}$ on \mathbf{A}_{sf} contained in \mathbf{V} , making this term non-local. A Taylor expansion given by

$$\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{y}} = \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{y} \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} : \nabla \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}} + \dots \quad (\text{A.7})$$

may be employed and, when introduced back into Eq. (A.6) together with the fact that

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{fs}} \mathbf{n} dA = -\nabla \langle 1 \rangle = -\nabla \varepsilon_f \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{fs}} \mathbf{n} \mathbf{y} dA = -\nabla \langle \mathbf{y} \rangle \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{fs}} \mathbf{n} \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} dA = -\nabla \langle \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} \rangle \quad (\text{A.10})$$

the average form of the mass conservation equation of species A takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot \left[\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\varepsilon_f \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f - \nabla \langle \mathbf{y} \rangle \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{1}{2} \nabla \langle \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} \rangle : \nabla \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f - \dots + \frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \tilde{c}_{O_2} dA \right) \right] \\ & - k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

With the purpose of simplifying this last equation, orders of magnitude can be employed to determine the important contributions among all the diffusive terms. Indeed, the following estimates can be derived

$$\varepsilon_f \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f = \mathbf{O} \left(\varepsilon_f \frac{\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{L} \right) \quad (\text{A.12a})$$

$$\nabla \langle \mathbf{y} \rangle \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f = \mathbf{O} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_f r_0}{L} \frac{\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{L} \right) \quad (\text{A.12b})$$

$$\nabla \langle \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} \rangle : \nabla \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f = \mathbf{O} \left(\left(\frac{\varepsilon_f r_0}{L} \right)^2 \frac{\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{L} \right) \quad (\text{A.12c})$$

On the basis of the scale hierarchy, it is not hard to deduce that Eq. (A.11) can be simplified to

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot \left[\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\varepsilon_f \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + \frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \tilde{c}_{O_2} dA \right) \right] \\ & - k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

In order to progress to a form of this last expression involving $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ only, the order of magnitude of \tilde{c}_{O_2} shall be obtained in comparison to that of $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$. To do so, B.C. 1 in Eq; (5e) can be rewritten as

$$-\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \tilde{c}_{O_2} - k_{2c} \tilde{c}_{O_2} c_{Re} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f c_{Re} + k_{2a} c_{Re} - k_{2a} c_E^t \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Orders of magnitude of the deviation and average normal fluxes at \mathbf{A}_{sf} can be estimated as

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \tilde{c}_{O_2} = \mathbf{O} (\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \tilde{c}_{O_2} / \ell_p) \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f = \mathbf{O} (\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f / L) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

This can be used in Eq. (A.14) to obtain an order of magnitude estimate of \tilde{c}_{O_2} given by

$$\tilde{c}_{O_2} = \mathbf{O} \left(\frac{(\ell_p/L) \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{1 + \mathbf{O} (k_{2c} \ell_p c_{Re} / \mathcal{D}_{O_2})}, \frac{(k_{2c} \ell_p c_{Re} / \mathcal{D}_{O_2}) \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{1 + \mathbf{O} (k_{2c} \ell_p c_{Re} / \mathcal{D}_{O_2})}, \frac{(k_{2a} \ell_p c_E^t / \mathcal{D}_{O_2})}{1 + \mathbf{O} (k_{2c} \ell_p c_{Re} / \mathcal{D}_{O_2})} \right) \quad (\text{A.17})$$

Noticing that $k_{2a} \ll k_{2c}$ and from the above estimate, it can be clearly seen that if the kinetic number, Ki is such that

$$Ki = \frac{k_{2c} \ell_p c_E^t}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \ll 1 \quad (\text{A.18})$$

then $\tilde{c}_{O_2} \ll \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ at \mathbf{A}_{sf} . Under these circumstances, Eq. (A.13) can be simplified to the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot \left[\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\varepsilon_f \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + \frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \tilde{c}_{O_2} dA \right) \right] \\ & - k_{2c} a_v \langle \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

In this equation, a close attention needs to be dedicated to the first of the three reactions terms which involves a non-local area integral. When the Taylor expansion of Eq. (A.7) is introduced in this integral, it comes

$$\langle \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} = \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}} + \langle \mathbf{y} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} : \nabla \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f |_{\mathbf{x}} + \dots \quad (\text{A.20})$$

394 For the second and third terms on the right hand side, the following estimates can be made

$$\langle \mathbf{y} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \ll r_0 \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$\langle \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} = r_0^2 \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \quad (\text{A.22})$$

so that

$$\langle \mathbf{y} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \ll \mathbf{O} \left(\frac{r_0}{L} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \right) \ll \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \quad (\text{A.23a})$$

$$\langle \mathbf{y} \mathbf{y} c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} : \nabla \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f = \mathbf{O} \left(\left(\frac{r_0}{L} \right)^2 \right) \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \ll \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \quad (\text{A.23b})$$

This shows that the dominant term in the expansion in Eq. (A.20) is $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}$. As a consequence the average equation (A.19) can be simplified to the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot \left[\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\varepsilon_f \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + \frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \tilde{c}_{O_2} dA \right) \right] \\ & - k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.24})$$

The boundary condition at the solid-fluid interface (Eq. (A.14)) can be written as

$$-\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \tilde{c}_{O_2} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f c_{Re} + k_{2a} c_{Re} - k_{2a} c_E^t \quad (\text{A.25})$$

In addition, taking into account the above order of magnitude estimate, the averaged mass conservation equation for the enzyme is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}}{\partial t} = & - (k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a}) \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2c} \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \\ & + (k_{1c} + k_{2a}) c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.26})$$

395 At this stage, the model remains unclosed since \tilde{c}_{O_2} is still present in the averaged mass
396 balance equation (A.24).

397 **Step 3: Closure**

The idea is now to form an IBVP (*i.e.* a closure problem) on \tilde{c}_{O_2} which solution can be inserted into the averaged equation in order to get a closed macroscopic model. This can be achieved by subtracting Eq. (A.24) divided by ε_f and Eq. (A.26) from their corresponding pore-scale equivalents in Eqs. (5d) and (5a), respectively and by using the boundary condition under the form of equation (A.25). Moreover, since the purpose is not to solve the closure problem on the entire structure of characteristic length-scale L but, rather, on a representative unit cell of the structure of characteristic length-scale ℓ_R , the external boundary condition shall be replaced by a periodic boundary condition on \tilde{c}_{O_2} (see Chap. 1 in [45]), yielding

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{c}_R}{\partial t} = - (k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a} + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f) \tilde{c}_R - k_{2c} \tilde{c}_{O_2} \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} \quad (\text{A.27a})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \tilde{c}_{O_2}}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot (\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \tilde{c}_{O_2}) - \varepsilon_f^{-1} \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \varepsilon_f \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f - \varepsilon_f^{-1} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \tilde{c}_{O_2} dA \right) \\ & + \varepsilon_f^{-1} k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + \varepsilon_f^{-1} k_{2a} a_v (\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - c_E^t) \quad \text{in } \mathbf{V}_f \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.27b})$$

$$-\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \tilde{c}_{O_2} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f c_{Re} + k_{2a} c_{Re} - k_{2a} c_E^t \quad \text{at } \mathbf{A}_{sf} \quad (\text{A.27c})$$

$$\tilde{c}_{O_2}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \tilde{c}_{O_2}(\mathbf{r} + \ell_R \mathbf{e}_i, t) \quad (\text{A.27d})$$

398 to which an initial condition must be added. Here \mathbf{e}_i denotes one of the unit basis vectors.
399 To obtain Eq. (A.27a), the decomposition $c_{Re} = \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + \tilde{c}_R$ was employed in conjunction
400 with the fact that $\tilde{c}_{O_2} \ll \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$.

To simplify this problem, the following orders of magnitude can be employed

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \tilde{c}_{O_2}) = \mathbf{O} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \tilde{c}_{O_2}}{\ell_p^2} \right) \quad (\text{A.28a})$$

$$\varepsilon_f^{-1} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \tilde{c}_{O_2} dA \right) = \mathbf{O} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}_{O_2} \tilde{c}_{O_2}}{\varepsilon_f L \ell_p} \right) \quad (\text{A.28b})$$

which, based on the length-scale hierarchy, indicates that the latter term is negligible with respect to the former. Moreover, the diffusive volume source $\varepsilon_f^{-1} \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \varepsilon_f \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ and of the diffusive surface source $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ can be compared by analyzing their respective contribution per unit volume of the porous medium. The corresponding order of magnitude estimates are given by

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{V}_f} \varepsilon_f^{-1} \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \varepsilon_f \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f dV = \mathbf{O} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_f \mathcal{D}_{O_2}}{L^2} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \right) \quad (\text{A.29a})$$

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f dA = \mathbf{O} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}{\ell_p L} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \right) \quad (\text{A.29b})$$

showing that the diffusive volume source has a negligible contribution. In addition, when the process is considered at a time scale constrained by

$$t \gg \max \left(\frac{\ell_p^2}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}, \frac{1}{k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a} + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f} \right) \quad (\text{A.30})$$

it is not hard to deduce that both unsteady terms can be neglected in Eqs. (A.27a) and (A.27b) so that the closure problem becomes steady. Finally, since $\tilde{c}_{O_2} \ll \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$, it follows that $k_{2c} \tilde{c}_{O_2} \ll k_{1c} + k_{1a} + k_{2a} + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$. As a consequence, Eq. (A.27a) yields $\tilde{c}_R \ll \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}$ and the closure problem takes the form

$$\nabla^2 \tilde{c}_{O_2} = -\frac{\varepsilon_f^{-1} k_{2c} a_v}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - \frac{\varepsilon_f^{-1} k_{2a} a_v}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} (\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - c_E^t) \quad \text{in } \mathbf{V}_f \quad (\text{A.31a})$$

$$-\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \tilde{c}_{O_2} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + k_{2c} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} (\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - c_E^t) \quad \text{at } \mathbf{A}_{sf} \quad (\text{A.31b})$$

$$\tilde{c}_{O_2}(\mathbf{r}) = \tilde{c}_{O_2}(\mathbf{r} + \ell_{rev} \mathbf{e}_i) \quad (\text{A.31c})$$

This problem has a linear structure, so the solution on \tilde{c}_{O_2} can be sought in terms of a linear combination of the sources under the form

$$\tilde{c}_{O_2} = \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f + s \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + h (\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - c_E^t) \quad (\text{A.32})$$

401 \mathbf{b} , s and h being the closure variables which can be chosen to obey the following boundary
402 value problems

Problem I

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{b} = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathbf{V}_f \quad (\text{A.33a})$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{b} = -\mathbf{n} \quad \text{at } \mathbf{A}_{sf} \quad (\text{A.33b})$$

$$\langle \mathbf{b} \rangle^f = 0 \quad (\text{A.33c})$$

$$\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r} + \ell_{rev} \mathbf{e}_i) \quad (\text{A.33d})$$

403

Problem II

$$\nabla^2 s = -\frac{\varepsilon_f^{-1} k_{2c} a_v}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \quad \text{in } \mathbf{V}_f \quad (\text{A.34a})$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla s = -\frac{k_{2c}}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \quad \text{at } \mathbf{A}_{sf} \quad (\text{A.34b})$$

$$\langle s \rangle^f = 0 \quad (\text{A.34c})$$

$$s(\mathbf{r}) = s(\mathbf{r} + \ell_{rev} \mathbf{e}_i) \quad (\text{A.34d})$$

404

Problem III

$$\nabla^2 h = -\frac{\varepsilon_f^{-1} k_{2a} a_v}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \quad \text{in } \mathbf{V}_f \quad (\text{A.35a})$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla h = -\frac{k_{2a}}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}} \quad \text{at } \mathbf{A}_{sf} \quad (\text{A.35b})$$

$$\langle h \rangle^f = 0 \quad (\text{A.35c})$$

$$h(\mathbf{r}) = h(\mathbf{r} + \ell_{rev} \mathbf{e}_i) \quad (\text{A.35d})$$

405 Note that the conditions in Eqs. (A.33c), (A.34c) and (A.35c) result from the fact that
406 $\langle \tilde{c}_{O_2} \rangle^f = 0$ and are required for both closure problems to have a unique solution.

407 **Step 4: Macroscopic model**

408 When the representation of \tilde{c}_{O_2} is reported back into the average equation (A.24), one
409 finally obtains the following closed macroscopic equation for $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} &= \nabla \cdot (\varepsilon_f \mathbf{D}_{eff} \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f) + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{s} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}) \\ &+ \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{h} (\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - c_E^t)) \\ &- k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.36})$$

with the effective parameters \mathbf{D}_{eff} and \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{h} given by

$$\mathbf{D}_{eff} = \mathcal{D}_{O_2} \left(\mathbf{I} + \frac{1}{V_f} \int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} b dA \right) \quad (\text{A.37})$$

$$\mathbf{s} = \frac{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}{V} \left(\int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} s dA \right) \quad (\text{A.38})$$

$$\mathbf{h} = \frac{\mathcal{D}_{O_2}}{V} \left(\int_{\mathbf{A}_{sf}} \mathbf{n} h dA \right) \quad (\text{A.39})$$

where \mathbf{b} , s and h are solution of the closure problems *I*, *II* and *III* in Eqs. (A.33), (A.34) and (A.35) respectively. Moreover, from Eq. (A.34b), the order of magnitude of s can be estimated to be $s = \mathbf{O}(k_{2c} \ell_p / \mathcal{D}_{O_2})$ and from Eq. (A.38), one gets $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{O}(k_{2c})$. This leads to an order of magnitude estimate for the second term on the right hand side of Eq. (A.36) given by $\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{s} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}) = \mathbf{O}\left(\frac{k_{2c}}{L} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}\right)$ while the order of magnitude of the macroscopic reactive term is $k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} = \mathbf{O}\left(\frac{k_{2c}}{\ell_p} \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}\right)$ with the idea that $a_v = \mathbf{O}(\ell_p^{-1})$. The same estimate can be made for \mathbf{h} . On the basis of the scale hierarchy, this indicates that the macroscopic diffusion/reaction equation for $\langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f$ may finally be written as

$$\varepsilon_f \frac{\partial \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\varepsilon_f \mathbf{D}_{eff} \cdot \nabla \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f) - k_{2c} a_v \langle c_{O_2} \rangle^f \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} - k_{2a} a_v \langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf} + k_{2a} a_v c_E^t \quad (\text{A.40})$$

410 The average equation for $\langle c_{Re} \rangle_{sf}$ is given by Eq. (A.26).

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